

Aroma-active compounds in Russian sturgeon (*Acipenser gueldenstaedtii*) raised in recirculating aquaculture systems

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ABSTRACT

The rearing system affects the nutritional and sensorial qualities of the Russian sturgeon (*Acipenser gueldenstaedtii*), a niche yet commercially valuable aquaculture species for caviar production. In the present work, we aimed to comprehensively characterize the odorant composition of fillets from Russian sturgeon raised in a recirculating aquaculture system (RAS) and discuss potential sources and formation pathways. A total of 114 odorants were detected through the application of combined sensory-instrumental analyses, of which 88 were successfully identified and 20 substances were found to be among the most potent odor constituents. The most dominant odorants were assigned to several specific substance classes, including aldehydes, alcohols, terpenes, ketones, organic acids, lactones, heterocycles, aromatic hydrocarbons, and sulfur-containing aldehydes. The compounds (*E*)-hex-2-enal, (*Z*)-hept-4-enal, cuminaldehyde, non-3-yn-1-ol, 3-carene, 2-methylisoborneol, geosmin, oct-1-en-3-one, nonan-3-one, (*Z*)-1,5-octadien-3-one, octane-2,3-dione, nonan-2-one, hexanoic acid, γ -crotonolactone, γ -octalactone, 2-acetyl-thiazoline, methional, and (2*E*,4*Z*,7*Z*)-trideca-2,4,7-trienal had high flavor dilution factors and are described for the first time as potent odor-active compounds associated with the Russian sturgeon. Overall, oct-1-en-3-one, (*Z*)-1,5-octadien-3-one, octane-2,3-dione, nonan-2-one, 2-methylisoborneol, and hexanoic acid had the highest flavor dilution factors. This study offers a basis for future development in the sturgeon RAS industry from the perspective of flavor characterization by providing deep insights into the fundamental composition and origins of the complex world of aquaculture fish aroma.

1. Introduction

Sturgeon is the common name for ray-finned fishes belonging to the Acipenseridae family (class: Actinopterygii, order: Acipenseriformes), which originated 200 million years ago during the Jurassic period [1]. The high economic value of caviar and lack of management of its trade have led to overexploitation and a decline in wild sturgeon populations [2]. Since 1997, the production of caviar from the wild supply of sturgeon has been forbidden based on the conservation principles of the Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora (CITES) [3]. Consequently, aquaculture-derived caviar production has increased [4], and modern aquaculture techniques have led to diversification of the market [2]. A variety of aquaculture production systems are currently employed, including flow-through (FT) systems, recirculating aquaculture systems (RAS), cages, FT/RAS mixtures, and

ponds, which represent 36 %, 21 %, 18 %, 11 %, and 7 %, respectively, of production [5]. The system by which sturgeons are reared can affect their growth and maturity, as well as the quality of the caviar. For example, production of Russian sturgeon (*Acipenser gueldenstaedtii*) using a combination of RAS/cages has been linked to a reduction in puberty time, an improvement in caviar quality, a rise in the percentage of eggs retrieved, and an increase in the size of oocytes compared with only RAS farming [6]. In contrast, RAS farming was better suited for producing sturgeon flesh [6].

Due to the high nutritional value of its meat and its relatively high market price, sturgeon is becoming more important commercially, and demand is increasing [7,8]. Nevertheless, only a few studies have described the quality parameters of sturgeon raised in RAS. For example, fillets from Siberian sturgeon (*Acipenser baerii*) reared in RAS were approximately 77 % moisture, 19 % protein, and 3 % fat [7]. A few studies

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have aimed to characterize the aroma profile and volatile compounds of sturgeon, focusing on the gradual change in the sturgeon meat due to storage [9]. For example, Hou et al. [10] used solid-phase microextraction and gas chromatography–mass spectrometry (SPME-GC-MS) to study volatiles in sturgeon stored for up to 9 days at 4 °C. They detected more than 40 volatile organic compounds and noted that heptanal, nonanal, and acetophenone increased with storage time [10]. The authors discussed the potential contribution of these compounds to the perceived aroma of the fish, but they did not apply a specific methodological approach for odor analysis. In another study, the authors analyzed how specific spoilage organisms influence quality parameters, including volatile profiles, of Siberian sturgeon [11]. Using SPME-GC-MS, the authors detected 35 volatile compounds. Once again, however, they did not use an approach that would allow the overall composition of odor-active (trace) compounds to be determined. More recently, Li et al. [12] investigated the effect of thermal processing on fillets from hybrid sturgeon (*Acipenser gueldenstaedtii* × *Acipenser schrenckii*) reared in an indoor pool, which provided insights into flavor regulation in thermally processed sturgeon products. The authors used a combination of sensory evaluation and solid-phase microextraction and gas chromatography–mass spectrometry/olfactometry (SPME-GC-MS/O), a technique dedicated to odor analysis. The raw meat was described as meaty, fishy, grassy, oily/fatty, fresh, earthy, visceral, salty, umami, and ammonia/rancid odor attributes. Moreover, a total of 39 compounds were detected in raw sturgeon meat, of which organic acids were the main volatile components [12].

The relationship between the aroma profile and odor-active compounds in the flesh of Russian sturgeon reared in RAS has yet to be investigated sufficiently, primarily because researchers have not undertaken a comprehensive comparison of quantitative data to the sensory parameters of the respective compounds. Moreover, for the analysis of odorant compounds in food, it is important to avoid the generation of artifacts or odorant degradation. To address this issue, the method of solvent-assisted flavor evaporation (SAFE) has been used previously as a mild extraction technique to isolate odor-active compounds from rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*) meat and skin [13], raw and cooked red mullet (*Mullus barbatus*) [14], and salmon fillets [15]. To the best of our knowledge, however, no studies have provided a comprehensive elucidation of odorant compounds in Russian sturgeon raised in RAS farms using this technique. In the present study, we aimed to characterize the odorant composition of Russian sturgeon raised in RAS to obtain a thorough understanding of their sources and formation pathways. In the first step, the aroma profile of Russian sturgeon fillets was evaluated based on a descriptive sensory analysis. Then, odorant compounds were characterized by gas chromatography–olfactometry (GC-O) and ranked according to their potential odor contribution via aroma extract dilution analysis (AEDA). Finally, odorants of interest were further identified via two-dimensional gas chromatography–mass spectrometry/olfactometry (GC-GC-MS/O), which allows the detection of odor-active compounds at trace levels, and identified odorants that coeluted with odorless compounds.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Chemicals

The reference compounds used in this study and their suppliers were as follows: dichloromethane (DCM; VWR Chemicals, Darmstadt, Germany), pentanal 97 %, (1S,5S)-6,6-dimethyl-2-methylidenebicyclo[3.1.1]heptane (β -pinene) 99 %, pentane-2,3-dione 97 %, hexanal 98 %, 1,4-xylene 99.5 %, 1,3-xylene 99.5 %, 3,7,7-trimethylbicyclo[4.1.0]hept-3-ene (3-carene) 90 %, pent-1-en-3-ol 99 %, (*E*)-pent-3-en-2-ol 96 %, heptanal >92 %, (4R)-1-methyl-4-prop-1-en-2-ylcyclohexene ((*R*)-limonene) 97 %, 1,3,3-trimethyl-2-oxabicyclo[2.2.2]octane (1,8-cineole) 99 %, (*E*)-hex-2-enal 98 %, octan-3-one \geq 98 %, (*Z*)-hept-4-enal 98 %, 1-methyl-4-propan-2-ylbenzene (*p*-cymene) 99 %, 1,2,4-trimethylbenzene (pseudocumene) 98 %, 3-hydroxybutan-2-one (acetoin),

oct-1-en-3-one 50 %, heptan-2-ol \geq 97 %, (*E*)-pent-2-en-1-ol 95 %, (*E*)-hept-2-enal 96 %, nonan-3-one 99 %, octane-2,3-dione 97 %, (*E*)-hex-3-en-1-ol 98 %, 6-methylhept-5-en-2-one 99 %, nonan-2-one \geq 99 %, 3-methylsulfanylpropanal (methional), acetic acid 99 %, decanal, (2*E*,4*E*)-hepta-2,4-dienal 88 %, benzaldehyde >99.5 %, (*E*)-non-2-enal >97 %, undecanal 97 %, butane-2,3-diol 98 %, (1*R*,2*R*,4*R*)-1,2,7,7-tetramethylbicyclo[2.2.1]heptan-2-ol (2-methylisoborneol) 98 %, 4-methyl-1-propan-2-ylcyclohex-3-en-1-ol (terpinen-4-ol) 95 %, oxolan-2-one (γ -butyrolactone) > 99 %, (2*E*,6*E*)-nona-2,6-dienal 95 %, 2-methylbutanoic acid 98 %, 5-methyl-2-propan-2-ylcyclohexan-1-ol (menthol) 99 %, nonan-1-ol >98 %, 3-methylbutanoic acid 99 %, (2*E*,4*E*)-nona-2,4-dienal 85 %, dodecanal 92 %, 2H-furan-5-one (γ -crotonolactone) 98 %, tridecanal 95 %, 4-propan-2-ylbenzaldehyde (cuminaldehyde) 98 %, (4*S*,4*S*,8*A*,8*R*)-4,8a-dimethyl-1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8-octahydronaphthalen-4a-ol (geosmin) \geq 97 %, (2*E*,4*E*)-deca-2,4-dienal 85 %, phenylmethanol (benzyl alcohol) 99 %, hexanoic acid 99.5 %, (1*R*,4*R*,6*R*,10*S*)-4,12,12-trimethyl-9-methylidene-5-oxatricyclo[8.2.0.0.4,6]dodecane (caryophyllene oxide) 95 %, 1,3-benzothiazole (benzothiazole) 96 %, (5*Z*)-6,10-dimethylundeca-5,9-dien-2-one ((*Z*)-geranylacetone) > 97 %, 5-pentylloxolan-2-one (γ -nonalactone) > 98 %, octanoic acid 98 %, 2,6-dimethylnaphthalene 99 %, 1,4-dimethylnaphthalene 95 %, 4-methoxybenzaldehyde (*p*-anisaldehyde) 98 %, (*E*)-3-phenylprop-2-enal ((*E*)-cinnamaldehyde) 99 %, 4-methylphenol (*p*-cresol) 98 %, (2*R*)-4-hydroxy-2,3-dimethyl-2*H*-furan-5-one (sotolone) 97 % (Sigma-Aldrich, Steinheim, Germany); oct-1-en-3-ol 98 %, 2-ethylhexan-1-ol \geq 99 %, butanoic acid >99.5 %, hexan-1-ol \geq 99 %, nonanal 95 %, undecan-1-ol 99.5 %, dodecan-1-ol 98 %, phenol 99 %, 5-methyl-2-propan-2-ylphenol (thymol) 99 % (Fluka, Steinheim, Germany); 2-methylpropanoic acid 99 %, 1-phenylethanone (acetophenone) 98 % (SAFC, Steinheim, Germany); 1-(4,5-dihydro-1,3-thiazol-2-yl)ethanone (2-acetyl-2-thiazoline) > 98.0 %, non-3-yn-1-ol > 99 %, pyrrolidin-2-one \geq 98.0 %, (3*R*)-3-hydroxy-4,4-dimethylloxolan-2-one (pantolactone), 2-(4-methyl-1,3-thiazol-5-yl)ethanol (4-methyl-5-thiazoleethanol) 98 %, cumene >99 %, 1,2,3,5-tetramethylbenzene \geq 70 %, (1*R*,4*E*,9*S*)-4,11,11-trimethyl-8-methylidenebicyclo[7.2.0]undec-4-ene (β -caryophyllene) 80 %, (*E*)-hept-3-enoic acid \geq 90 % (TCI Deutschland GmbH, Eschborn, Germany); propanoic acid 99 % (Riedel-de Haen GmbH, Seelze, Germany); (1*R*,2*R*,4*R*)-1,7,7-trimethylbicyclo[2.2.1]heptan-2-ol (isoborneol) (Givaudan, Vernier, Switzerland); octanal 99 % (Thermo Fischer GmbH, Kandel, Germany); 3-(3-pentylloxiran-2-yl)prop-2-enal (*tr*-4,5-epoxy-(*E*)-2-decenal) 97 %, (2*E*,4*Z*,7*Z*)-trideca-2,4,7-trienal, (5*Z*)-octa-1,5-dien-3-one ((*Z*)-1,5-octadien-3-one) 99 % (AromaLab, Planegg, Germany), 1,3,5-trimethylbenzene (mesitylene) 98 % (VWR International GmbH, Portland, OR, USA); 5-butyloxolan-2-one (γ -octalactone) (EGA Chemie, Steinheim, Germany); and pentadecanoic acid 99 % (Alfa Aesar, Karlsruhe, Germany). One commercial Sniffin' Stick test, pen number 16, was purchased (Burghart Messtechnik GmbH, Holm, Germany). A solution of a homologous series of the *n*-alkanes (C6-C31; all supplied from Sigma-Aldrich) in pentane was used to determine the retention indices (RIs).

2.2. Samples

All samples were collected from a commercial RAS farm in France in October 2022. On this particular farm, juvenile sturgeons are raised in 35-m³ tanks until they reach 20 months of age. Three juvenile male sturgeons were caught from a large commercial tank with conspecifics, each with an average weight of 3000 \pm 500 g. The fish had not undergone depuration and had a distinct smell. The fish were slaughtered immediately, placed separately in a sterile bag, and frozen for 1 month at -20 °C until transportation to the laboratory, which was done on ice packs within 1 day. Then, fish fillets were kept at -20 °C until analysis (for a maximum duration of 5 months).

2.3. Solvent extraction and SAFE

The procedure used to extract volatile compounds from the fillets was adapted from the method described by Ref. [13]. Portions of each fish fillet were separately cut into approximately 1 cm³ and then finely minced in a mortar and pestle with the addition of liquid nitrogen until a powder with small pieces was obtained. Fifty grams of powder was weighed and submitted to extraction one time with 100 mL of DCM by dynamic maceration for 30 min at room temperature (RO 10P, IKA, Staufen, Germany). Subsequently, the extract was collected separately and distilled via SAFE [16]. After SAFE, the distillate was dried over anhydrous sodium sulfate (Na₂SO₄). Prior to chromatographic analysis, the total volume of each distillate was reduced to approximately 100 µL via Vigreux distillation and micro-distillation at 50 °C.

2.4. Methods for the identification of odorants

2.4.1. Gas chromatography-olfactometry/flame ionization detector (GC-O/FID) and AEDA

Separation of constituent volatiles of the sample extract distillates was performed using a TRACE GC Ultra (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA). The capillaries were: DB-5 (30 m × 0.32 mm × 0.25 µm; Agilent J&W, Santa Clara, CA, USA) or DB-FFAP (30 m × 0.32 mm × 0.25 µm; Agilent J&W). The initial temperature for both columns was 40 °C, maintained for 2 min. Then, the temperature was raised at 8 °C/min to 250 °C and held there for 10 min, or to 240 °C and held there for 8 min, for DB-5 and FFAP, respectively. The injection volume was 2 µL (cold-on-column technique) and the flow rate of the helium carrier gas was 2.2 mL/min. At the end of the capillary, a Y-splitter was used so that the GC effluent was divided 1:1 between the odor detection port (ODP) and the flame ionization detector (FID) through two uncoated and deactivated fused silica capillaries (0.5 m × 0.2 mm). The FID and ODP were maintained at 250 and 270 °C, respectively. Experts were asked to sniff the undiluted distillate. GC-O analyses were performed by three experts to avoid possible anosmia-related biases. They were recruited from the trained panel of the Chair of Aroma and Smell Research, Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg (FAU), Germany.

The potential impact of individual odor-active compounds on the overall aroma of the fish fillets was determined by a dilution-to-threshold AEDA method [17], which was performed by one of the three panelists using the DB-FFAP column. Flavor dilution (FD) factors were thereby obtained based on a series of dilutions: the undiluted distillate (FD = 1) was diluted stepwise with DCM (1:3; v/v), resulting in 10 solutions for each sample yielding FD factors ranging from 3 to 2187. The FD factor corresponding to each odorant is represented as the last dilution in which the odor-active compound was perceivable by means of GC-O.

2.4.2. Gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS)

One-dimensional GC-MS was performed using an Agilent 7890 A GC system (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, USA), equipped with either a DB-FFAP (30 m × 0.25 mm × 0.25 µm; Agilent J&W, Santa Clara, CA, USA) or DB-5 (30 m × 0.25 mm × 0.25 µm; Agilent J&W, Santa Clara, CA, USA) column and a CIS4 injection system (Gerstel GmbH & Co. KG, Mülheim an der Ruhr, Germany). The same GC oven temperature program described in section 2.4.1 was used. The analyses were performed in splitless mode with helium as a carrier gas at a flow rate of 1.0 mL/min. The injection was carried out using an MPS 2 XL autosampler (Gerstel GmbH & Co. KG) and the injection volume was 1 µL. The GC system was coupled to an Agilent MSD 5975C. The electron ionization mass spectra (EI) were recorded in scan mode (*m/z* 40–400) with an ionization energy of 70 eV.

2.4.3. Two-dimensional gas chromatography-mass spectrometry/olfactometry (GC-GC-MS/O)

Further analyses focusing on the trace compounds were performed using a GC-GC-MS/O consisting of two Agilent 7890B GC systems coupled to an Agilent 5977B MS (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, USA). The first GC oven was installed with a DB-FFAP column (30 m × 0.32 mm × 0.25 µm; J&W GC Columns, Santa Clara, CA, USA). The second GC was equipped with a DB-5 capillary column (30 m × 0.25 mm × 0.25 µm; J&W GC Columns, Santa Clara, CA, USA). Helium was used as the carrier gas at a flow rate of 2.5 mL/min. The distillates (1 or 2 µL) were injected automatically using the cold-on-column technique at 40 °C and a multipurpose sampler MPS 2XL (Gerstel GmbH & Co. KG, Mülheim an der Ruhr, Germany). After 2 min, the temperature of the first oven was increased to 240 °C at a rate of 8 °C/min and held there for 5 min. After passing the pre- (uncoated, deactivated fused silica) and main column, the effluent was split into two parts, one reaching the cryogenic trapping system (CTS) and thus the second GC, and the other one reaching the ODP (270 °C) and FID (250 °C). The elution range containing the odorants of interest was transferred to a CTS 1 cryo-trap system (Gerstel GmbH & Co. KG, Mülheim an der Ruhr, Germany) by means of an MCS2 multicolumn switching system (Gerstel GmbH & Co. KG). The odorants were transferred into the second oven by thermal desorption (250 °C). The temperature of the second GC was held at 40 °C for 1 min, then raised to 250 °C at 8 °C/min, and held for 1 min. The second GC was connected directly to the MS and an ODP (Gerstel GmbH & Co. KG, Mülheim an der Ruhr, Germany). The EI mass spectra were generated at 70 eV ionization energy in scan mode (*m/z* 35–400).

2.4.4. Identification of odorants

The odorant compounds were identified based on comparison of the odor quality (O), the RIs on two capillaries with different polarities (DB-FFAP and DB-5), and mass spectra with those of authentic reference compounds. The criteria for the tentative identification of compounds are given in section 3. The RI was calculated for each odor-active compound by means of a reference series of homologous alkanes (C₆-C₃₀) [18].

2.5. Sensory evaluation

2.5.1. Panelists

Seven panelists (all female; age range: 22–34 years) were recruited from the trained panel of the Chair of Aroma and Smell Research (FAU). The panelists were trained in weekly sessions to perceive, describe, and rate odor qualities and intensities of about 150 odorants, covering typical odorants from both the food and non-food sectors. All panelists were healthy and exhibited normal olfactory function at the time of the assessments.

2.5.2. Aroma profile analysis

For the sensory evaluation, approximately 25 g (±0.05 g) of fish fillet was presented in a 120-mL Weck glass (WECK GmbH u. CO KG, Bonn, Germany) covered with aluminum foil to avoid light-induced oxidation processes and an influence on the sensory ratings by the appearance of the sample. The aroma profile analysis was performed according to ISO 13299:2016–09 and complemented by the determination of the overall smell intensity. Briefly, sensory analyses were carried out during two sessions in a well-lit and ventilated sensory room at 21 °C. Samples were coded with a random three-digit number before being presented to the panelists for orthonasal evaluation. In the first session, the panelists were invited to name their individually perceived odor impression of the sturgeon fillet sample. Then, the appropriate scale and the listed odor attributes were discussed by the panel; attributes with an agreement of >50 % were selected. In the second session, the panelists were asked to evaluate the overall odor intensity and pleasantness of the perceived smell. The scale ranged from 0 (no perception) to 10 (strong perception) for the overall odor intensities, and the pleasantness was rated from

0 (dislike) to 5 (neutral) and 10 (like). The intensities of the selected attributes were rated on a scale from 0 (no perception) to 10 (strong perception), where each attribute's intensity could not exceed the overall intensity. The averages of these ratings were plotted in a spider-web diagram. As references for the ratings of the odor attributes earthy, green/grassy, soapy, and fishy, three odor pens containing isoborneol, hexanal, and nonanal, and one commercial Sniffin' Stick no. 16 (Burghart Messtechnik GmbH) were used, respectively. For the fatty attribute, aqueous solutions containing acetoin (0.2 and 0.4 $\mu\text{L}/\text{mL}$, depending on the panelist's sensitivity to this compound) were presented in 120-mL Weck glasses (WECK GmbH u. CO KG, Bonn, Germany) and used as reference. For the sea-water-like/alga-like attribute, no reference was used and it was rated based on the concept alone, known to each panelist.

3. Results

3.1. Aroma profile and sensory evaluation

The panel selected the odor attributes earthy, fishy, fatty, sea-water-like/alga-like, green/grassy, and soapy to describe the aroma of the sturgeon fillets. The aroma profile is shown in Fig. 1. Overall, the odor attributes were rated with average intensities of 1.4–5.3. The dominant odor attributes in the sturgeon samples were fishy and sea-water-like/alga-like, both scored with an average of 5.3. The odor attributes earthy, fatty, green/grassy, and soapy were all rated with lower average intensity ratings, ranging from 1.4 to 3.8.

The overall odor intensity and pleasantness ratings of the Russian sturgeon samples are displayed in Fig. 2; the average was 7.5 and 1.6, respectively. The average pleasantness score demonstrated a general, considerable dislike of the smell. The raw data for the aroma profile, overall odor intensity, and pleasantness ratings are shown in Table S1.

3.2. Characterization of odor-active compounds in Russian sturgeon fillets

Olfactory assessment with GC-O revealed 114 compounds with an FD factor from 0 to 2187 (Table 1). Five of these substances were only detectable in the undiluted extract (FD 1), whereas 109 compounds had an FD factor of ≥ 3 (Table 1). Eighty-six compounds were identified by

comparison of their respective RIs on two different columns, mass spectra and odor qualities with their corresponding reference compounds. However, 23 compounds could not be identified due to their low concentrations. Three compounds were tentatively identified based on their RIs on one column, odor qualities, and mass spectra, namely (*E*)-pent-2-en-1-ol, pent-1-en-3-ol, and acetic acid. Furthermore, two compounds were tentatively identified based on their RIs on two different columns and the odor qualities of the corresponding reference compounds, namely (*Z*)-1,5-octadien-3-one and sotolone.

Comparing the odorant compounds on basis of the determined FD factors, there were 20 odorants with a FD factor > 243 (Fig. 3). Among them, oct-1-en-3-one (mushroom-like), (*Z*)-1,5-octadien-3-one (geranium leaf-like, green, metallic), octane-2,3-dione (strawberry-, licorice-, mint-like), nonan-2-one (fruity, soapy), 2-methylisoborneol (earthy, musty), and hexanoic acid (fruity, musty) had with the highest FD factor (2187). Next, there were eight odorant compounds with an FD factor of 729, namely 3-carene (citrus-like, eucalyptus-like), (*Z*)-hept-4-enal (fishy, fatty), oct-1-en-3-ol (mushroom-like), methional (cooked potato-like), γ -crotonolactone (fruity, soapy, green), 2-acetyl-2-thiazoline (popcorn-like), geosmin (earthy, moldy), and (2*E*,4*Z*,7*Z*)-trideca-2,4,7-trienal (decayed, fishy). In addition, six compounds were identified with an FD factor of 243, namely hexanal (grassy), (*E*)-hex-2-enal (fruity, apple-like, banana-like), nonan-3-one (fruity, blue mold cheese-like), non-3-yn-1-ol (fatty, geranium leaf-like), cuminaldehyde (cumin-like, fatty), and γ -octalactone (coconut-like). The most potent odorants did not coincide with the main peaks in the chromatogram, indicating that less abundant compounds were among the most important odor contributors (Fig. 4). Fig. 5 shows the most frequent odor descriptors of the odorants based on AEDA (cf. Table 1).

Considering their chemical structure, we classified the identified odorants into nine different groups (Fig. S1). Aldehydes contained the highest number of identified substances, comprising the homologous series of aldehydes from pentanal to tridecanal, as well as others (16, 19, 28, 43–45, 54, 63, 69, 71, 83, 86, 89, and 93). The remaining compounds were classified as alcohols (11, 12, 26, 27, 29, 33, 37, 41, 50, 59, 67, 73, 74, 79, 82, and 92); terpenes (7, 10, 14, 15, 20, 48, 51, 52, 56, 58, 70, 72, 78, and 98); ketones (5, 18, 23, 25, 30–32, 35, 36, 57); organic acids (40, 55, 61, 62, 75, 85, 91, and 112); lactones (53, 65, 76, 87, 88, 97); heterocyclic compounds (66, 80, 90, and 102); aromatic hydrocarbons (8, 9, 17, 21, 22, 38, 81, and 84); and sulfur-containing aldehydes (39) (Table 1). Most of the above-mentioned substances are reported here for the first time in RAS-reared finfish as well as in Russian sturgeon (see Table 1).

4. Discussion

The purpose of the present study was to investigate the odorant composition and to describe the aroma profile of fillets from Russian sturgeon raised in a RAS. Below, we discuss the potential sources and formation pathways of the identified odorants. GC-O analyses led to the detection of 114 odorants; thereby, AEDA revealed 20 substances as potentially important odor contributors.

4.1. Comparison of the sensory and analytical results

The trained panel described the smell of the Russian sturgeon fillet with the odor attributes earthy, fishy, fatty, sea-water-like/alga-like, green/grassy, and soapy. Although the fish were caught in a freshwater aquaculture farm, sea-water-like/alga-like was used as a descriptor. The origin of the samples was unknown to the panelists, and there were no other saltwater fish available for comparison. In addition, sea-water-like/alga-like can be related to fish due to information that has been experienced previously, that is, sensory expectations [19].

The odor qualities of the detected odor-active compounds correlated very closely with the odor descriptors reported by the panelists. The earthy odor attribute, for example, corresponded well with the detection

Fig. 1. The aroma profile of fillets from Russian sturgeon reared in a recirculating aquaculture system (RAS). The average intensity ratings of all panelists ($n = 7$) are on a scale from 0 (no perception) to 10 (strong perception).

Fig. 2. The overall odor intensity and pleasantness ratings of fillets from Russian sturgeon reared in a recirculating aquaculture system (RAS). The scale ranges from 0 (no perception) to 10 (strong perception) for the overall odor intensity, and from 0 (dislike) to 5 (neutral) and 10 (like) for pleasantness. The data are displayed as the average \pm standard deviation of the sensory evaluation ($n = 7$).

of several earthy-smelling compounds, namely 2-methylisoborneol (51), terpinen-4-ol, isoborneol (58), and geosmin (70). The panelists selected isoborneol as a reference for the earthy descriptor, without any information about the sample's composition. The compounds 2-methylisoborneol and geosmin have previously been associated with earthy odor impressions in fish and have low odor thresholds [20]. It is likely that 2-methylisoborneol and geosmin were the primary contributors to the earthy odor impression in the samples due to their relatively high FD factors (2187 and 729, respectively).

The attributes fishy and sea-water-like/alga-like are likely related to the presence of the potent fishy smelling odorants (*Z*)-hept-4-enal (19), and (2*E*,4*Z*,7*Z*)-trideca-2,4,7-trienal (93) (both with an FD factor of 729). Fish-like impressions are frequently reported for freshwater and saltwater aquatic animals, as well as in wild-caught and aquaculture productions [21]. Additionally, other substances identified in the present study, namely hexanal (6), pent-1-en-3-ol (11), heptanal (13), oct-1-en-3-one (25), nonanal (34), oct-1-en-3-ol (37), decanal (42), and (2*E*,4*E*)-hepta-2,4-dienal (43), have been reported in the literature as contributors to an undesirable fishy odor [22].

The odor attribute fatty is likely to be related to several fatty smelling compounds identified, notably heptanal (13), (*Z*)-hept-4-enal (19), (*E*)-hept-2-enal (28), (2*E*,4*E*)-hepta-2,4-dienal (43), (*E*)-non-2-enal (45), (2*E*,6*E*)-nona-2,6-dienal (54), (2*E*,4*E*)-nona-2,4-dienal (63), non-3-yn-1-ol (67), cuminaldehyde (69), (2*E*,4*E*)-deca-2,4-dienal (71), and octanoic acid (91). The panelists, however, selected the butter-like smelling acetoin as the reference for the fatty descriptor. The FD obtained for this compound was low (FD = 9). Nonetheless, this compound could contribute to the overall odor of the fillets, because AEDA is only a screening technique, and matrix or mixture effects present upon sensory evaluation of the fillet may not be adequately mirrored by AEDA for acetoin. Moreover, this molecule is rather volatile and reactive, so it might have been recovered insufficiently during sample workup and thus compromised in terms of FD factor representation. Furthermore, complex mixtures of odorants can, in general, evoke odor impressions that are not represented by their individual components [23]. Additional experiments would be necessary to evaluate such potential effects.

The attributes green/grassy could be related to the compounds (*E*)-

hex-3-en-1-ol (grassy) (33), hexan-1-ol (green) (29), (*Z*)-1,5-octadien-3-one (geranium leaf-like) (31), β -caryophyllene (48), as well as the grassy smelling hexanal (6). Out of these, hexanal and (*Z*)-1,5-octadien-3-one had the highest FD factors (243 and 2187, respectively). Furthermore, the cucumber-like smelling (2*E*,6*E*)-nona-2,6-dienal and (*E*)-non-2-enal may have contributed to the odor attribute green.

Several soapy smelling compounds were identified, including the homologous series of the aldehydes heptanal, octanal, nonanal, decanal, undecanal, dodecanal, and tridecanal, with changes in their odor characteristics depending on the chain length. In addition, other compounds with a soapy odor impression may have contributed to the attribute, namely 1,4-xylene, heptan-2-ol, mesitylene, pseudocumene, nonan-1-ol, (*Z*)-geranylacetone, undecan-1-ol, and nonan-2-one.

Overall, all odor descriptors used to describe the odor of the Russian sturgeon fillets in this study were in accordance with the predominant odor qualities of the odorant compounds perceived by means of GC-O. Furthermore, the present results are in line with odor components described for aquatic animals and the flavor wheel of fish raised in RAS [21,24]. Of note, there are numerous reports that suggest synergistic effects contribute to the smell of aquaculture products. For example, (*E*,*Z*)-2,6-nonadienal, 1-penten-3-one, (*Z*)-4-heptenal, and (*E*,*E*)-2,4-heptadienal were individually not responsible for fishy malodors, but might cause fishy off-flavors as a result of a combinatory effect [25]. Therefore, future studies including quantification of relevant odor compounds and aroma recombination and omission experiments are needed to evaluate these effects and their importance for the odor of Russian sturgeon fillets. Quantitative experiments will also allow researchers to determine the overall variation in the concentration of aroma compounds in different individuals/fish tanks. However, this was not the aim of the present study: We focused on determining the aroma profile of sturgeon produced in RAS and identifying odor-active substances, as described in section 4.2.

4.2. Possible formation pathways and sources of odor-active compounds in Russian sturgeon raised in a RAS

In this study, we have reported the first comprehensive odorant

Table 1

Odor-active compounds identified in fillets from Russian sturgeon raised in a recirculating aquaculture system (RAS). The table includes the odor quality, flavor dilution (FD) factor, the retention indices (RIs), and the identification criteria for each odorant.

No. ^a	Odorant	Odor quality ^b	FD factor ^c	RI ^d		Identification criteria ^e	Previously identified source ^g
				FFAP	DB-5		
1	Unknown	Butter-like, fishy ^f	27	993	–		
2	Pentanal	Yeast dough-like, malty	27	998	842	RI, O, MS, RC	
3	Unknown	Butter-like, green ^f	81	1035	–		
4	Unknown	Green ^f	27	1048	–		
5	Pentane-2,3-dione	Butter-like	9	1057	840	RI, O, MS, RC	RAS
6	Hexanal	Grassy	243	1091	807	RI, O, MS, RC	RAS, RS
7	β -Pinene	Eucalyptus-like	9	1103	987	RI, O, MS, RC	
8	1,4-Xylene	Fuel-like, glue stick-like	9	1128	856	RI, O, MS, RC	RAS, RS
9	1,3-Xylene	Green, plastic-like	9	1134	861	RI, O, MS, RC	
10	3-Carene	Citrus-like, eucalyptus-like	729	1141	1233	RI, O, MS, RC	
11	Pent-1-en-3-ol	Plastic-like	9	1148	–	RI ¹ , O, MS, RC	RS
12	(E)-Pent-3-en-2-ol	Nutty	27	1162	703	RI, O, MS, RC	RAS
13	Heptanal	Soapy, fatty	27	1172	895	RI, O, MS, RC	RAS, RS
14	Limonene	Orange-peel-like, lemon-peel-like	9	1183	1021	RI, O, MS, RC	RAS
15	1,8-Cineole	Eucalyptus-like	1	1190	982	RI, O, MS, RC	
16	(E)-Hex-2-enal	Fruity, apple-like, banana-like	243	1216	874	RI, O, MS, RC	RS
17	Cumene	Fuel-like	3	1223	893	RI, O, MS, RC	RAS
18	Octan-3-one	Fruity, banana-like	3	1232	933	RI, O, MS, RC	RAS
19	(Z)-Hept-4-enal	Fishy, fatty	729	1239	902	RI, O, MS, RC	RAS
20	p-Cymene	Oregano-like	27	1248	1029	RI, O, MS, RC	
21	Mesitylene	Soapy, fruity ^h	1	1252	918	RI, O, MS, RC	
22	Pseudocumene	Soapy, fruity, green ^h	27	1258	984	RI, O, MS, RC	RAS
23	Acetoin	Butter-like	9	1268	776	RI, O, MS, RC	RAS
24	Octanal	Citrus-like, soapy	9	1281	1008	RI, O, MS, RC	RAS, RS
25	Oct-1-en-3-one	Mushroom-like	2187	1294	983	RI, O, MS, RC	RAS
26	Heptan-2-ol	Soapy, citrus-like	9	1306	905	RI, O, MS, RC	
27	(E)-Pent-2-en-1-ol	Fruity, green apple-like, cheesy	27	1316	–	RI ¹ , O, MS, RC	RAS, RS
28	(E)-Hept-2-enal	Green apple-like, fatty, bitter almond-like	27	1319	959	RI, O, MS, RC	RAS
29	Hexan-1-ol	Green apple-like, green, almond-like	9	1331	878	RI, O, MS, RC	RAS, RS
30	Nonan-3-one	Fruity, blue mold cheese-like	243	1350	1071	RI, O, MS, RC	
31	(Z)-1,5-Octadien-3-one	Geranium leaf-like, green, metallic	2187	1363	977	RI ¹ , O, RC	RAS
32	Octane-2,3-dione	Strawberry-like, licorice-like, mint-like	2187	1369	979	RI, O, MS, RC	RAS
33	(E)-Hex-3-en-1-ol	Grassy	27	1381	851	RI, O, MS, RC	RAS
34	Nonanal	Soapy, citrus-like	27	1384	1098	RI, O, MS, RC	RAS, RS
35	6-Methylhept-5-en-2-one	Fruity	3	1391	973	RI, O, MS, RC	
36	Nonan-2-one	Fruity, soapy	2187	1399	1077	RI, O, MS, RC	RAS
37	Oct-1-en-3-ol	Mushroom-like	729	1427	995	RI, O, MS, RC	RAS, RS
38	1,2,3,5-Tetramethylbenzene	Medicinal, petroleum-like	81	1433	1083	RI, O, MS, RC	
39	Methional	Cooked potato-like	729	1440	909	RI, O, MS, RC	RAS
40	Acetic acid	Vinegar-like	9	1450	–	RI ¹ , O, MS, RC	RAS
41	2-Ethylhexan-1-ol	Eucalyptus-like, band aid-like	27	1467	1040	RI, O, MS, RC	RAS, RS
42	Decanal	Soapy	9	1483	1214	RI, O, MS, RC	RAS, RS
43	(2E,4E)-Hepta-2,4-dienal	Fatty, fruity	1	1493	1013	RI, O, MS, RC	RAS
44	Benzaldehyde	Marzipan-like, almond-like	81	1504	968	RI, O, MS, RC	RAS, RS
45	(E)-Non-2-enal	Fatty, cucumber-like, cardboard-like	81	1514	1156	RI, O, MS, RC	RAS
46	Propanoic acid	Vinegar-like, fruity, cheesy	81	1529	936	RI, O, MS, RC	RAS
47	Unknown	Butter-like, fatty ^f	9	1543	–		
48	β -Caryophyllene	Carrot-like, green	27	1564	1432	RI, O, MS, RC	RAS
49	Undecanal	Coriander-like, soapy, citrus-like	1	1571	1331	RI, O, MS, RC	RAS
50	Butane-2,3-diol	Fruity, solvent-like	1	1579	786	RI, O, MS, RC	RAS
51	2-Methylisoborneol	Earthy, musty	2187	1586	1181	RI, O, MS, RC	RAS
52	Terpinen-4-ol	Earthy, moldy, cork-like	9	1593	1177	RI, O, MS, RC	
53	γ -Butyrolactone	Soapy, fruity ^h	9	1604	914	RI, O, MS, RC	RAS
54	(2E,6E)-Nona-2,6-dienal	Fatty, cucumber-like	81	1607	1147	RI, O, MS, RC	
55	Butanoic acid	Cheesy, sweaty	9	1621	790	RI, O, MS, RC	RAS
56	Menthol	Eucalyptus-like	3	1629	1193	RI, O, MS, RC	
57	Acetophenone	Marzipan-like, flowery	81	1632	1063	RI, O, MS, RC	RAS
58	Isoborneol	Earthy	3	1636	1179	RI, O, MS, RC	RAS
59	Nonan-1-ol	Soapy, citrus-like	3	1643	1174	RI, O, MS, RC	
60	Unknown	Soapy, rubber-like ^f	3	1646	–		
61	3-Methylbutanoic acid	Cheesy	27	1654	861	RI, O, MS, RC	
62	2-Methylbutanoic acid	Apple-like, fruity	3	1664	871	RI, O, MS, RC	RAS
63	(2E,4E)-Nona-2,4-dienal	Fatty, nutty	9	1686	1207	RI, O, MS, RC	
64	Dodecanal	Coriander-like, soapy	27	1704	1397	RI, O, MS, RC	RAS, RS
65	γ -Crotonolactone	Fruity	729	1727	888	RI, O, MS, RC	
66	2-Acetyl-2-thiazoline	Popcorn-like, roasty	729	1738	1119	RI, O, MS, RC	RAS
67	Non-3-yn-1-ol	Fatty, geranium leaf-like	243	1754	1184	RI, O, MS, RC	RAS
68	Tridecanal	Soapy, waxy	9	1765	1518	RI, O, MS, RC	RAS
69	Cuminaldehyde	Cumin-like, fatty	243	1781	1245	RI, O, MS, RC	
70	Geosmin	Earthy, moldy	729	1808	1408	RI, O, MS, RC	RAS
71	(2E,4E)-Deca-2,4-dienal	Fatty, deep fried	9	1816	1319	RI, O, MS, RC	RAS
72	(Z)-Geranylacetone	Soapy	27	1832	1441	RI, O, MS, RC	RAS, RS

(continued on next page)

Table 1 (continued)

No. ^a	Odorant	Odor quality ^b	FD factor ^c	RI ^d		Identification criteria ^e	Previously identified source ^g
				FFAP	DB-5		
73	Undecan-1-ol	Soapy, coriander-like	9	1848	1364	RI, O, MS, RC	
74	Benzyl alcohol	Bitter almond-like	9	1876	1044	RI, O, MS, RC	
75	Hexanoic acid	Fruity, musty	2187	1880	986	RI, O, MS, RC	RAS
76	γ -Octalactone	Coconut-like	243	1904	1260	RI, O, MS, RC	
77	Unknown	Nutty, soapy ^f	9	1921	–	–	
78	Caryophyllene oxide	Musk-like, flowery	27	1933	1588	RI, O, MS, RC	
79	Dodecan-1-ol	Soapy	27	1946	1473	RI, O, MS, RC	
80	Benzothiazole	Rubber-like, car tire-like	27	1954	1240	RI, O, MS, RC	RAS, RS
81	2,6-Dimethylnaphthalene	Anise-like, ethereal, fennel-like	9	1963	1414	RI, O, MS, RC	
82	Phenol	Ink-like	9	1983	1002	RI, O, MS, RC	
83	<i>Tr</i> -4,5-Epoxy-(<i>E</i>)-2-decenal	Metallic	81	1996	1375	RI, O, MS, RC	RAS
84	1,4-Dimethylnaphthalene	Rubber-like, naphthalene-like	9	2004	1454	RI, O, MS, RC	RAS
85	(<i>E</i>)-Hept-3-enoic acid	Sweaty, cheesy, waxy	3	2013	1165	RI, O, MS, RC	
86	<i>p</i> -Anisaldehyde	Almond-like	3	2017	1269	RI, O, MS, RC	
87	γ -Nonalactone	Coconut-like	27	2022	1358	RI, O, MS, RC	RAS
88	Pantolactone	Smoked-ham-like, savory-like	9	2030	1028	RI, O, MS, RC	RAS
89	(<i>E</i>)-Cinnamaldehyde	Cinnamon-like	9	2035	1293	RI, O, MS, RC	RAS, RS
90	Pyrolidin-2-one	Fruity, flowery, plastic ^h	81	2039	1075	RI, O, MS, RC	
91	Octanoic acid	Musty, coriander-like, fatty	9	2048	1198	RI, O, MS, RC	
92	<i>p</i> -Cresol	Horse-stable-like, fecal	81	2070	1092	RI, O, MS, RC	
93	(2 <i>E</i> ,4 <i>Z</i> ,7 <i>Z</i>)-Trideca-2,4,7-trienal	Decayed, fishy	729	2096	1579	RI, O, MS, RC	RAS
94	Unknown	Nutty ^f	27	2109	–	–	
95	Unknown	Plastic-like ^f	3	2127	–	–	
96	Unknown	Moldy, green, fatty ^f	27	2145	–	–	
97	Sotolone	Savory, celery-like	9	2182	1105	RI, O, RC	RAS
98	Thymol	Thyme-like	9	2191	1298	RI, O, MS, RC	
99	Unknown	Earthy ^f	9	2238	–	–	
100	Unknown	Coriander-like ^f	27	2257	–	–	
101	Unknown	Rubber-like, oil-like, pepper-like ^f	9	2276	–	–	
102	4-Methyl-5-thiazoleethanol	Meat-broth-like, savory	3	2310	1386	RI, O, MS, RC	RAS
103	Unknown	Fatty ^f	9	2333	–	–	
104	Unknown	Rubber-like, caramel-like ^f	9	2371	–	–	
105	Unknown	Metallic ^f	9	2425	–	–	
106	Unknown	Fecal, rubber-like ^f	9	2470	–	–	
107	Unknown	Rubber-like ^f	27	2505	–	–	
108	Unknown	Caramel-like ^f	9	2589	–	–	
109	Unknown	Plastic-like ^f	9	2626	–	–	
110	Unknown	Fecal, sweaty ^f	27	2658	–	–	
111	Unknown	Green, fecal, sweaty ^f	27	2679	–	–	
112	Pentadecanoic acid	Waxy	9	2824	1833	RI, O, MS, RC	
113	Unknown	Plastic-like ^f	3	2882	–	–	
114	Unknown	Sweaty, medicinal ^f	3	2988	–	–	

^a The numbering is based on elution from the DB-FFAP capillary.

^b The odor quality described by Chair of Aroma and Smell Research at FAU database.

^c The FD factor based on the DB-FFAP capillary. It ranges from 1 to 2187, where 1 refers to the non-diluted sample.

^d The linear RI is presented separately for the DB-FFAP and DB-5 capillaries.

^e Identification was based on comparison of the RIs in the two columns, the odor quality (O), the mass spectrum (MS) obtained by gas chromatography–mass spectrometry (GC-MS) or two-dimensional gas chromatography–mass spectrometry/olfactometry (GC-GC-MS/O analysis), and reference compound (RC).

^f The odor quality was determined by one trained panelist at the sniffing port.

^g This compound has been reported in previous publications on recirculating aquaculture systems (RAS) or Russian sturgeon fillets (RS).

^h The odor quality was determined by one trained panelist at the sniffing port due to the toxicity of the pure substance for attribute determination.

ⁱ The compounds were tentatively identified based on comparison of the RI from one column, the O, the MS obtained by GC-MS or GC-GC-MS/O analysis, and the RC.

characterization, based on the FD factor to evaluate odor contributions, in Russian sturgeon raised in a RAS. In general, there are different pathways for the release or formation of odorants in the complex system of RAS production.

Regarding the substances identified in the present study, the group of saturated and unsaturated aldehydes was most dominant in the GC-O analysis, followed by alcohols, terpenes, and ketones. The results are in agreement with those previously reported for Russian sturgeon [26]. Specifically, aldehydes are products of enzymatic oxidation or autoxidation of lipids, and they have been reported to contribute to fish odor because of their low odor thresholds [27,28]. We identified 23 aldehydes in our analyses, including 9 saturated aliphatic, 10 unsaturated aliphatic, and 4 aromatic aldehydes. The large number and high FD factors of fatty acid–derived aldehydes are in line with previous reports on aquaculture products [13,29]. For example, a previous study applying SPME-GC-MS to study volatiles in fresh and stored sturgeon

reported that the content of heptanal, nonanal, and acetophenone increased with storage time, while the content of hexanal and octanal decreased. Consistently, Hou et al. [10] considered these compounds to be potential biomarkers for sensory and qualitative evaluation of sturgeon products. Additionally, hexanal, nonanal, decanal, heptanal, and octanal were also described in sturgeon fillets treated by low temperature vacuum heating, in which the concentration of these aldehydes decreased with increasing temperature, which was also accompanied by a reduction in off-flavor [26]. In the present study, hexanal (6), (*E*)-hex-2-enal (16), (*Z*)-hept-4-enal (19), cuminaldehyde (69), and (2*E*,4*Z*,7*Z*)-trideca-2,4,7-trienal (93) were identified with an FD factor > 243. They vary from grassy (e.g., hexanal) to fishy-fatty (e.g., (*Z*)-hept-4-enal) smelling, which may also contribute to off-flavor. Indeed, hexanal (6), (*E*)-hex-2-enal (16), and (*Z*)-hept-4-enal (19) have frequently been reported in aquaculture and freshwater animals [21], while we have reported cuminaldehyde (69) here for the first time as a

Fig. 3. Odorant compounds with their respective flavor dilution (FD) factor identified in fillets from Russian sturgeon raised in a recirculating aquaculture system (RAS). Only odorants with an FD > 243 are included.

potent odorant in Russian sturgeon and for RAS. Cuminaldehyde has been reported to exert antibacterial activity against food-borne pathogens and has been used to protect cultured shrimp against white spot syndrome virus [30]. Additional experiments conducted in fish feed are required to determine whether cuminaldehyde originates from external sources in Russian sturgeon raised in RAS.

Alcohols were the second largest odorant class identified in the present study, among which only oct-1-en-3-ol (37) and non-3-yn-1-ol (67) had an FD factor > 243. Although both compounds have already been reported in RAS, we have identified non-3-yn-1-ol for the first time in Russian sturgeon. In general, the formation of alcohols in fish is related to the breakdown of polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs) by lipoxygenases [31]. Additionally, Zhang et al. [11] reported oct-1-en-3-ol (37) and (*E*)-pent-2-en-1-ol (27) in hybrid sturgeon (*Acipenser baerii*) fillets. The authors suggested that these compounds are possible markers of spoilage by *Pseudomonas mandelii* in these fillets [11]. Specifically, oct-1-en-3-ol (mushroom-like) has been reported as a potent odorant in freshwater and marine fish, and it is considered to be an odorant substance that strongly contributes to fishy and rancid odors [21,22,32].

In the present study, fourteen terpenes (including terpene derivatives) were identified. Among them, 3-carene (10), 2-methylisoborneol (51), and geosmin (70) had an FD factor > 729 and are reported here for the first time in Russian sturgeon. Terpenes in fish originate from an external source, likely from feed and phytoplankton, and have been described extensively in seafood, and various methods have been proposed to control them [33,34]. The earthy/moldy smelling compounds 2-methylisoborneol (51) and geosmin (70) are among the most common off-flavor compounds in fish and RAS [35], and their concentration levels depend on a variety of parameters, including feed, temperature, lipid content, fish size and species, and microorganisms involved [36,37]. The citrus-like and eucalyptus-like smelling 3-carene (10) was identified in the present study for the first time as potent

odorant compound in Russian sturgeon and for RAS. Nevertheless, this compound was described previously in phytoplankton biomass collected from fish ponds [33].

Ketones and diketones were also identified as potent odorant compounds. These findings are in line with previous results, in which these substances have been described in a large number of wild and farmed aquatic animals [27,38]. The formation of ketones is associated with autoxidation of PUFAs and might also be related to microbial spoilage, in which unpleasant and unacceptable off-flavors were reported [39]. Moreover, ketones like oct-1-en-3-one, (*Z*)-1,5-octadien-3-one and octane-2,3-dione might contribute intensively to the overall aroma of seafood and have been associated with off-flavor notes, with a negative impact on sensory quality [21,40,41]. In the present study, oct-1-en-3-one (25), nonan-3-one (30), (*Z*)-1,5-octadien-3-one (31), octane-2,3-dione (32), and nonan-2-one (36) are reported for the first time as potent odorants in Russian sturgeon (FD factor > 243). Among these compounds, only nonan-2-one was previously detected in the study of microbial diversity and phospholipids effects on flavor profile of caviar from hybrid sturgeon (*Huso dauricus* × *Acipenser schrencki*) [42].

Although nine organic acids were identified in Russian sturgeon, only hexanoic acid (75) had an FD factor > 243; we have reported it here for the first time in Russian sturgeon. Moreover, 3-methylbutanoic acid (61), (*E*)-hept-3-enoic acid (85), octanoic acid (91), and pentadecanoic acid (112)—which vary regarding smell impression from cheesy (e.g., 3-methylbutanoic acid) to musty-fatty (e.g., octanoic acid), were identified in the present study for the first time in Russian sturgeon and RAS. Carboxylic acids have been reported to occur naturally in aquatic animals and have been stated to contribute to the fishy odor of freshwater fish [27,43,44].

Six lactones were identified, of which γ -crotonolactone (65) and γ -octalactone (76) had an FD factor > 243. Lactones have been detected in many aquatic animals from fresh and salt water, as well as in fish feeds [21,45]. This compound class can originate from the oxidation of fatty

Fig. 4. Gas chromatography–mass spectroscopy chromatogram of the sturgeon fillet extract corresponding to a flavor dilution (FD) factor of 3 on a DB-FFAP column. The retention times of the odorants with an FD factor > 243 are highlighted. The numbering is according to Table 1.

acids or be absorbed by the fish through the feed [45,46]. For γ -crotonolactone, it is worth noting that this compound is used in preparations for therapy and prevention of aeromoniasis and to foster fish growth [47]. We have identified both γ -octalactone and γ -crotonolactone for the first time in the present study as potent odorant compounds in Russian sturgeon and for RAS.

Among the four heterocyclic compounds identified, 2-acetyl-thiazoline (66) had an FD factor > 729. Our findings are consistent with a previous study in which the authors described thiazolines and thiazoles (e.g., 2-acetyl-thiazoline and benzothiazole) as potent contributors to the aroma of roasted shrimp [48]. In terms of formation pathways, these substances can arise from degradation between sulfur-containing amino compounds and carbonyls, such as thiamine and cysteine [49,50]. The compounds 2-acetyl-2-thiazoline (66), benzothiazole (80), pyrrolidin-2-one (90), and 4-methyl-5-thiazoleethanol (102) are described here for the first time as odorant compounds in Russian sturgeon.

Eight aromatic hydrocarbons were identified in the present study—1,3-xylene (9), cumene (17), mesitylene (21), pseudocumene (22), 1,2,3,5-tetramethylbenzene (38), 2,6-dimethylnaphthalene (81), and 1,4-dimethylnaphthalene (84)—although they were not very potent odorants (FD factor < 243). Our study is the first to report these substances in Russian sturgeon fillets. Among this class, we detected two polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) as a sub-class, namely 2,6-dimethylnaphthalene and 1,4-dimethylnaphthalene. Literature [11], has reported PAHs as off-odor contributors in fish and potential markers in hybrid sturgeon spoiled by *Pseudomonas fluorescens* during ice storage. The clarification of the chemical nature of the odorant compounds can now serve as a basis for future studies to understand the possible sources of these substances in sturgeon fillets, and the correlation with their presence in RAS.

Finally, one sulfur-containing aldehyde was identified, namely methional (39), with FD factor > 243 here for the first time as a potent odor in Russian sturgeon fillets. In previous studies, methional was reported as a potent odorant with high FD factor in hake (*Merluccius merluccius*) and sardine (*Sardinapilchardus*) and imparted an overall “fishy” odor character [51,52]. Regarding the formation pathways of this compound, methional is a Strecker aldehyde derived from methionine through the Maillard reaction [22,53].

In general, previous research on sturgeon fillets has focused on the impact of different post-harvest processes on the sensory quality of the fish. Indeed, a variety of odorant substances have been described as potential biomarkers of the quality of sturgeon products, such as hexanal, heptanal, octanal, nonanal, decanal, acetophenone, 2-ethylfuran, trichloromethane, ethyl acetate, PAHs, tetramethyl-pyrazine, oct-1-en-3-ol, (Z)-2-penten-1-ol, 1-(3,3-dimethylbicyclo [2.2.1] hept-2-yl)-ethanone, butylated hydroxytoluene, (E)-2-decenal, (E, E)-2,4-decadienal, (E)-2-undecenal, 1-heptyn-3-ol, formic acid, formamide, and 1,5-decadiyne [10–12,26]. Nevertheless, these previous studies have mostly focused on the post-harvest process, and on volatile compounds in general. By using methods targeting odor-active compounds in the samples, potent odorants in Russian sturgeon that might also contribute to the overall flavor and sensory quality of the fillets were identified. Among them, the following compounds are reported for the first time in Russian sturgeon: the aldehydes (E)-hex-2-enal (16), (Z)-hept-4-enal (19), cuminaldehyde (69) and (2E,4Z,7Z)-trideca-2,4,7-trienal (93); the alcohol non-3-yn-1-ol (67); the terpenes 3-carene (10), 2-methylisoborneol (51), and geosmin (70); the ketones oct-1-en-3-one (25), nonan-3-one (30), (Z)-1,5-octadien-3-one (31), octane-2,3-dione (32), and nonan-2-one (36); the lactones γ -crotonolactone (65) and γ -octalactone (76); the organic acid hexanoic acid (75); the heterocyclic compound 2-acetyl-thiazoline (66); and the sulfur-containing aldehyde

Fig. 5. Predominant descriptors of odorant compounds detected by aroma extract dilution analysis (AEDA). The area covered by each odor quality represents the number of times the odor descriptor was reported with respect to Russian sturgeon (cf. Table 1). Only descriptors occurring at least two times were considered.

methional (39). In addition, 3-carene, nonan-3-one, γ -crotonolactone, cuminaldehyde, and γ -octalactone are also reported for the first time in RAS.

Understanding the possible origins and pathways of odor development by chemical, biochemical, and microbiological processes in fish processing and post-harvest treatment is crucial to enable the control of external factors that influence the formation of volatile compounds and impact the quality of fish products. For Russian sturgeon, the origin and formation pathways have not been well investigated in fillets, especially in complex production processes such as RAS. Therefore, the findings of this study can serve as a basis for further targeted aroma investigations in Russian sturgeon and other selected fish species in RAS.

5. Conclusion

The present study revealed the presence of 114 odorants in fillets from Russian sturgeon reared in RAS, among which 20 substances had an FD factor >243 . These compounds included aldehydes, alcohols, terpenes, ketones, organic acids, lactones, heterocycles, aromatic hydrocarbons, and sulfur-containing aldehydes. Of these odorants, the compounds (*E*)-hex-2-enal, (*Z*)-hept-4-enal, cuminaldehyde, non-3-yn-1-ol, 3-carene, 2-methylisoborneol, geosmin, oct-1-en-3-one, nonan-3-one, (*Z*)-1,5-octadien-3-one, octane-2,3-dione, nonan-2-one, hexanoic acid, γ -crotonolactone, γ -octalactone, 2-acetyl-thiazoline, methional, and (2*E*,4*Z*,7*Z*)-trideca-2,4,7-trienal are described for the first time as odorant compounds in Russian sturgeon. Additionally, 3-carene, nonan-3-one, γ -crotonolactone, cuminaldehyde, and γ -octalactone are also described for the first time in RAS. Overall, oct-1-en-3-one, (*Z*)-1,5-octadien-3-one, octane-2,3-dione, nonan-2-one, 2-methylisoborneol, and hexanoic acid had the highest FD factors. The proposed emission sources for the investigated odorants are very diverse, and are most likely the result of oxidation processes.

This study shows that combinatory sensory and instrumental analyses of odorants are needed to obtain a fundamental understanding of the odorant composition in fish. In the aquaculture industry, this knowledge is crucial for future targeted development of improved manufacturing processes for seafood products that meet sensorial quality requirements and, consequently, consumer acceptance. In this context, this work represents the first time that odorants have been investigated in Russian sturgeon raised in RAS. Additional studies are required, in particular with regard to combining methods of sturgeon production raised in RAS and their impact on sensory quality. Moreover, sensory analyses can be conducted to understand the interaction between individual odorants and their influence on the overall perceived fish aroma. In this respect, the present study can be regarded as an important step toward the aroma characterization of Russian sturgeon raised in RAS.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Mariana Rodrigues da Silva: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Matteo Egiddi:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **Bastien Debeuf:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **Andrea Buettner:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Conceptualization. **Helene M. Loos:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jafr.2024.101443>.

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